

THE MONITORING OF DAMAGE PROCESSES IN CFRP COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

BY AMPLITUDE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This paper is concerned with damage accumulation monitored by A.E. technique during tensile tests on unidirectional and cross-plyed CFRP. The purpose of the study was to discriminate between the different mechanisms of fracture in composites by amplitude analysis of the recorded signals. Two approaches were considered, the first being the cumulative amplitude histograms obtained by using Pollock's equation and the second being the differential amplitude histograms for which a new method of analysis has been proposed. The first approach enabled the correlation of first ply failure with the appearance of a high amplitude distribution, the second revealed that even in a unidirectional CFRP, the main mechanism of degradation - fibre breakage - coexists with secondary phenomenon such as matrix cracking or interfacial failure.

Introduction

It is well known that damage produced in composite materials is of a complex nature and classical means of investigation used for homogenous materials - such as X-Ray analysis, U.S. scanning etc - are not always amenable. The acoustic emission technique has several specific advantages for example sensitivity and real time capability of damage investigation. The problem of discrimination between the different and often simultaneous mechanisms arises. Signal amplitude analysis offers the possibility of such a discrimination (1, 2, 3). The approach used in general is mainly qualitative as it involves a statistical analysis of the amplitude of the recorded signals. The usefulness of the results obtained depends on the theoretical means of analysis and modelling of distribution : some authors present the obtained results in terms of observed peak in the differential histograms, others prefer values of "b slope" obtained by plotting the amplitude events in a cumulative histograms, using the Pollock equation :

$$F(V) = N_0 \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right)^{-b} \quad (1)$$

where V_0 is the smallest detected amplitude, N_0 the total number of events and b a parameter which characterises the damage mechanism for a given material. Here we propose a new method of analysis, which takes better account of the mechanisms which must arise in composite failure. This analytical technique is based on a spectral approach of the differential histograms with the help of a new distribution function which unifies the two methods of analysis previously described = "main peak" and "b slope". By analysing both cumulative and differential histograms obtained on unidirectional an cross-plyed CFRP, different mechanisms of fracture can be discriminated.

Modelling

During an acoustic emission recording the signal amplitudes may vary over several orders of magnitude. Two functions can be used to describe the amplitude distribution, either a differential distribution function $f(V)$ defined by the number of events for which the amplitude is equal to the value V or a cumulative distribution function $F(V)$ defined by the number of events for which the amplitudes are equal or higher than the value V . These two functions are related by :

$$f(V) = - \frac{dF(V)}{dV} \quad (2)$$

Experimental results (4, 5) have shown that differential histograms present some symmetrical peaks. On a logarithmic scale the peaks consist of pairs of symmetrical linear lines of slope B and $-B$ positioned about x_0 on the the abscissa (4). Equation (1) cannot take into account such results since it is a continuously decreasing linear function. A new function is therefore proposed for the cumulative histograms :

$$G(V) = N_0 \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right)^{-b} \frac{V_a^{-b} + V_0^{-b}}{V_a^{-b} + V^{-b}} \quad (3)$$

For amplitudes such that $V \gg V_0$ and $V_0 \gg V_a$ that is to say, far from the top of the corresponding peak of the differential histograms :

Figure 1 : Differential amplitude distribution corresponding to equation 6 and showing the influence of the parameter b .

Figure 2 : Cumulative amplitude distribution corresponding to equation 4 and showing the influence of the parameter x_a .

$$\frac{V_a^{-b} + V_o^{-b}}{V_a^{-b} + V^{-b}} \approx \frac{V_a^{-b}}{V_a^{-b}} = 1$$

which leads to equation (1) which is a limiting case of this function. The main advantage of equation (3) is to give a corresponding symmetrical differential histogram which a maximum of n_o at V_a (4). When the amplitude is expressed in dB we have :

$$G(x) = N_o \frac{1 - \text{th } B \left(\frac{x - x_a}{2} \right)}{1 - \text{th } B \left(\frac{x_o - x_a}{2} \right)} \quad (4)$$

with $B = \frac{b \text{ Log } 10}{20}$

From equation (4) we can deduce :

$$-\frac{1}{N_o} \frac{dG(x)}{dx} = \frac{n(x)}{n_o} = \frac{B}{4} (1 - \text{th}^2 B \left(\frac{x - x_a}{2} \right)) \frac{1}{1 - \text{th } B \left(\frac{x_o - x_a}{2} \right)} \quad (5)$$

Putting :

$$\frac{n_o}{N_o} = \frac{B}{4} \frac{1}{1 - \text{th} B \left(\frac{x_o - x_a}{2} \right)}$$

We have :

$$g(x) = n_o \left[1 - \text{th}^2 B \left(\frac{x - x_a}{2} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

With logarithmic scales, the differential histogram is represented by two symmetrical linear parts of slope B and -B on each side of x_a . Hence each observed peak can be deconvoluted and correlated with x_a particular degradation mechanism. Figure 1 represents the influence of the parameter B on the slope of one peak whereas Figure 2 illustrates the effect of x_a on the cumulative histogram.

Experimental Details

Experiments have been conducted on flat notched plate specimens made from different types of prepreg. There were Ciba Geigy Fribredux 914 CTS and Vicotex 108 which have respectively a 180° and a 120° curing temperature. The samples were both unidirectional and cross-plyed. These latter specimens were examined using both acoustic emission and X-Ray analysis in an attempt to detect first ply failure and a comparison made of the results obtained with the two techniques. The stacking sequences were $(0^\circ_n, 90^\circ, \pm 45^\circ)_s$ with $n = 1, 2, 3$ and $(0,^\circ 90^\circ)_s$.

Some unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced polystyrylpyridine (PSP) specimens were also tested. The PSP specimens were made by the Société Nationale des Poudres et Explosifs, the cure temperature was 250°C. In all cases, the reinforcement was Toray T300 carbon fibres. The PSP resin is thermostable and is able to sustain higher temperature than more traditional epoxy resins.

All acoustic emission monitoring was made with a 3000 series Dunegan Endeveco system. A PZT differential transducer type D140 B was employed with a dominant frequency at 200 kHz. The system consisted of a 40 dB preamplifier with a frequency range of 100-300 kHz, an amplifier with adjustable gain and an impulse detector transforming all peaks exceeding the threshold (25 dB) at the output into digital pulses. The dB measurements were given in reference to a 1 μ V signal at the transducer. The analysis system was set to have a dead time of 100 μ s which allowed one event only to be counted for each series of pulses separated by less than 100 μ s

Experimental Results

Unidirectional samples.

The G (x) functions were recorded on logarithmic scales and the g(x) functions were recorded simultaneously on both linear and logarithmic scales. The results concerned both Vi 108 and PSP based composites using equation (6). The differential histograms approach has enabled the detection of several mechanisms during the tensile tests as several peaks were found with different values of B (Figures 3 and 4). It is remarkable that the positions of the different peaks are the same for the two materials and the corresponding B values are similar (Table 1) = the mechanisms recorded are the same but the proportion of each is different.

Table I. Coefficient b values obtained for the different detectable peaks for both materials.

Peaks (dB)	PSP	V_i
25	0,44	0,44
34	0,4	0,4
40	0,78	0,69
47	1,73	1,73
55	1,73	2,4
60	1,73	2,6

Figure 3 : Comparison of the differential amplitude histograms for a) PSP and b) epoxy based unidirectional composite material.

Figure 4 : Representation on logarithmic scales of the normal amplitude histograms obtained on a) PSP and b) epoxy based unidirectional composite material. The applied stress is equal to 588 and 1000 MPa respectively.

These results can be attributed to microcracking of the matrix ($x_a = 25$ dB, $x_s = 34$ dB) fibre breakage ($x_a = 40$ dB) and interfacial failure ($x_a = 47, 55$ and $x_s = 60$ dB). A high proportion of a events can be seen at low amplitudes for the PSP composites. This can be attributed to microcracking of the resin due to internal stresses enhanced by the curing cycle. The PSP matrix is very brittle ($K_{1C} = 0,28$ MPa) and the triaxial state of stress due to the difference of the coefficients of expansion of the matrix and the fibres is very important when the composite undergoes temperature variations between 200 or 300°C as is the case during its elaboration. For the V₁₀₈ material the main peak is displaced during the tensile test = at the start, the emission are centered around 25 dB, then, as the applied stress is increased, a more important proportion of events is observed around 40 dB due to fibre failure. It should be noted that cumulative histograms cannot distinguish all these different mechanisms since only one coefficient b was measured due to the smoothing effect of integration of the differential histogram. The value of b was equal to 2 corresponding to the end of the differential histograms.

Cross Plied Samples

The following results are concerned with 914 CTS prepreg based composites. It has been shown (3) that there is a clear difference between cumulative histograms obtained during tensile tests on unidirectional and cross-plyed (0, 90)_s samples. A high amplitude distribution can be detected for the latter materials leading to a point of inflexion in the histograms, however nothing of that kind can be detected for unidirectional samples. It seems probable that this difference is due to first ply failure. To confirm this assesment, tests were carried out on (0, 90)_s and (0_n, 90_n ± 45)_s samples the cumulative histograms recorded as a function of the applied stresses. Below a certain critical stress, the histograms are quite similar to the histogram

Figure 5 : Evolution of the cumulative amplitude histogram of acoustic emission obtained on a (0°, 90°)_s specimen as a function of stress during tensile testing.

obtained on unidirectional samples, above this critical stress, the second distribution at high amplitudes appears (Figure 5). The correlation between calculation of first ply failure, X-Ray analysis and these critical stresses are good as shown by Figure 6. For the kind of material, first ply failure (90°) is activated in tension and the rupture is catastrophic ; the acoustic emission detected is in real time. If shear stresses dominate as is the case for ($\pm 45^\circ$)_s composites for example, we detect the initiation of the ply failure, that is to say the decohesion of fibres and matrix and then their subsequent coalescence (6).

Figure 6 : First ply failure detection by acoustic emission compared to the theoretical determination for ($0^\circ_n, 90^\circ \pm 45^\circ_s$) composites.

Discussion

Figure 7 represents the theoretical influence of the position of a secondary peak on the shape of the cumulative histogram. The first distribution is centred around 25 dB since the second one is centred around 50, 60 and 70 dB. The ratio of emissions belonging to the first and the second peaks remains constant. Figure 8 examine the theoretical influence of the number of emissions of the secondary peak on the shape of the cumulative histogram. The first distribution is still centred around 25 dB and the second around 65 dB since the number of emissions of the second distribution increases. It can be seen from figure 5 that the experimental evolution corresponds to the case of a growing influence of the secondary peak without any shifting (Figure 8). This has also been observed on differential histograms obtained with unidirectional samples (Figure 3) : the peak corresponding to fibre breaks, for example still remains at 40 dB throughout the test whilst the energy released increases as the stress level is raised. It can be seen therefore that the relationship between energy and amplitude is not clear. From Figures 7 and 8 we can see that two mechanisms resulting in emission will induce more than two slopes in the cumulative histogram. Two distributions will give two uniform slopes characteristic of the mechanisms

Figure 7 : Theoretical influence of the position (x_{a2}) of a secondary peak on the shape of the cumulative histogram.

involved ($b_1 = 2$ for low amplitude and $b_2 = 1$ for high amplitude in the simulation shown in Figures 7 and 8). Another slope can exist between these domains but which corresponds to no distinct mechanism since the corresponding b value is a function of the number of events of the two extreme distributions. It should be clear therefore that although at a casual inspection Figure 5 seems to show the presence of three distinct mechanisms the above analysis reveals that only two really exist.

Figure 8 : Theoretical influence of the number of emission (N_2) of the secondary peak on the shape of the cumulative histogram.

Conclusion

A new way of modeling acoustic emission amplitude histograms has been described. Within the scope of this new theory, the Pollock equation is found to be a special case of the proposed model. Amplitude analysis enables first ply failure detection in real time and also it shows that even in a unidirectional composite, the main mechanisms of failure, that is to say fibre breakage, coexists with secondary phenomenon such as matrix microcracking around fibre breaks or interfacial failure.

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